

OPEN SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA FOR SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES - PREPARATION

WP1: Project Management and Technical
coordination

Data Management Plan

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Deliverable 1.2
Data Management Plan

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Introduction

The OPERAS-P project (early-Phase) will support OPERAS, furthering the development of the infrastructure in view of achieving the necessary scientific, technical and community maturity. OPERAS (open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities) objective is to establish a common framework for open scholarly communication, particularly in SSH.

OPERAS-P specific objectives are: producing the necessary documentation defining OPERAS strategy and implementation to support ESFRI application, supporting the preparation phase of the infrastructure by implementing a legal framework, a governance and support the implementation and coordination of services, prepare a long-term, evidence-based strategy for the development of the infrastructure and its services, ensure outreach and advocacy for open scholarly communication in SSH, developing a communication strategy on the infrastructure and supporting the expansion of the consortium, and enhancing innovation for the future of scholarly communication practices in SSH.

The main data collected will be survey data on one hand and reports on the other hand. Various surveys will be conducted to collect information on current usage, needs and expectations regarding SSH open access publishing practices. Based on these results, reports will describe the existing technological and functional landscape and also the prospective for the future OPERAS e-infrastructure.

I. Data Summary

Data produced within the OPERAS-P project will serve as first reference material for the design of the future OPERAS Research Infrastructure. Planned surveys and reports are meant to give a detailed information on both the landscape and the prospective for Open Access monographs in SSH.

- Reports: several tasks of the project have analytical reports as an outlet. These reports will be documents in known formats: PDF, ODT. Data volumes in this case will therefore be minimal and data origin will always be OPERAS-P partners.
- Surveys: Some outputs of the projects will be surveys be conducted among SSH European stakeholders: D2.3 Landscape Study, D2.4 Business Plan and KPIs, D6.2 Innovative Business model, D6.4 Report on innovative models of bibliodiversity in scholarly publications, D6.3 Report on innovative approach to FAIR data, D6.6 Report on quality assessment of innovative research in SSH.

Data type in this case will be: the questionnaire itself, the answers and the statistics results. All this data will be stored for potential reuse and verification. Data format for the storage will be CSV and PDF. The overall size should be lower than 100MB.

II. Fair Data

A. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

A naming policy has been adopted for all the files produced in the project. The policy is described in a deliverable named "Collaborative web platform".

Here is the extract regarding the naming policy: "Every file added to the OPERAS-P project and related to a WP should abide to some naming policies. This will facilitate the retrieval from the various tools used by the project (*Google Drive*, e-mail).

It's better to avoid spaces in the file names. It's possible to connect the different parts with underscores or dashes. When doing so, each word can be in lowercase.

Another possibility is to use the camel case. The filename should give some minimal information so that it can be easily identified and retrieved. Minimal information is:

- a code referring to the project, the WP and the task;
- the subject or title.

The file naming pattern will be the following (within brackets is the variable part):

OP [WP number.Task number] - [subject] - [subject] - ... - (final draft)

Details:

1. "OP" for OPERAS- project
2. Number of the Work Package (1, 2, 3, ...)
3. Number of the task (1, 2, 3, ...)
4. Producer (acronym of the participant: EKT, OE, MWS,...)
5. Subject section: a few words, connected with underscores or dashes
6. (Final version mention)

Example:

OP1.2-OE-collaborative_web-platform_final

The reports produced within the project are stored on the Zenodo European institutional repository (<https://zenodo.org/>). The repository allows for these service provisions:

- Handles each type of files - DOI identifiers automatic attribution - OAI-PMH harvesting
- Flexible licensing - 50GB space
- Community deposits (OPERAS community at:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/operaseu/?page=1&size=20>)

The other files and especially the data of the anonymised surveys (CSV, PDF and specific formats of the surveys software) are stored on the institutional French repository Nakala

(<https://www.nakala.fr>). This service managed by the CNRS Research Infrastructure Huma-Num (<http://www.huma-num.fr>) is able to produce and maintain:

- persistent identifiers: based on "handle" technology (<http://www.handle.net>);
- harvestable metadata: DC and QDC for OAI-PMH
- long term archiving

B. Making data openly accessible

All files will be public and openly accessible on the open repository mentioned above: <https://zenodo.org/communities/operaseu/?page=1&size=20>

Only exceptions are:

- files containing sensitive information on the partners involved and indicated as CO (confidential) in the H2020 grant agreement; these files will not be deposited.
- files of the surveys deposited will only be the anonymised versions (neither names or personal email address); raw anonymised data of the surveys will be accessible for processing with the open source software Limesurvey (<https://www.limesurvey.org/>).

C. Making data interoperable

Main metadata standard used will be the DublinCore generated by the institutional repositories; it will be used to describe the various documents.

D. Increase data reuse (through clarifying licenses)

- Embargo: no embargo.
- Third parties: as per the H2020 Grant Agreement, surveys anonymized data will be accessible to the OPERAS-P beneficiaries.
- Quality assurance: files use at least open format (ODT), standard format (PDF) or open source formats (Limesurvey); long term archiving will be taken care of by the open repositories.
- Licenses:
 - The public reports are made accessible under the Creative Commons license BY (attribution).
 - Works on the surveys (presentations, reports, etc.) are also made accessible

under the Creative Commons license BY (attribution).

- As per the declaration to the CNIL (French national institution for protecting digital data), access to the surveys will be limited to the beneficiaries (OE, OAPEN, EKT). No free license will be applicable.

III. Allocation of resources

The costs for making the data FAIR are covered by the FTE provisions of the OPERAS-P project.

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IV. Data Security

- Current backup: reports produced are edited and saved on the Google Drive application; files final version is also saved on local servers.
- Secure storage: the secure storage of the surveys data is locally provided by the CNRS (France); long term secure storage will be provided by the institutional repositories.

V. Ethical Aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former.

See 2.2.

